

Section-2 : Short Cases

Successful Treatment of Alopecia Areata in a Paediatric Patient with Homeopathic Medicine

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Abstract

This case report documents the successful homeopathic treatment of a 7 year old boy suffering from Alopecia areata. It is an autoimmune disorder that causes patchy hair loss on the scalp. This report emphasizes the importance of homeopathy as a safe and effective therapeutic option. The patient complained of hair loss in multiple areas of the head for about 2 months. Physical examination revealed that the patches were round and smooth, with no inflammation or redness. The detailed case-taking was performed by considering the individual symptoms and mental state of the patient and homeopathic principles & repertorisation of the case, homeopathic medicine *Natrum muriaticum* was prescribed. After the treatment was started, gradual improvement was observed in the patient's condition. Within months, new fine hair began to grow in the affected areas. After months of continued treatment. The treatment completely healed entirely and hair growth returned to normal. During this time, the patient did not experience any adverse side effects, and her overall health and mental state also improved. This case report concludes that homeopathy can be a highly effective and safe option in the treatment of alopecia areata. This case highlights the potential of homeopathy in paediatric skin diseases and provides an avenue for further research.

Keywords: Alopecia Areata, Homeopathy, Paediatric, Autoimmune disease, Homoeopathic Medicine.

Introduction

What is Alopecia:

Alopecia word used in medical for hair loss, which can occur on the scalp or any other part of the body. There are several types of alopecia and it can cause hair to fall out in patches or completely. Hair loss can be caused by stress, genetics, health problems, medications, hair damage, and many other factors.^{1,2}

Alopecia areata:

Alopecia areata is an autoimmune disease that causes hair loss on your body, but it most commonly affects the hair of scalp. Alopecia is a medical term for hair loss and areata means it occurs in small, irregular areas. Alopecia areata is not contagious.

Classifications:

- Alopecia barbae
- Alopecia ophiasis
- Alopecia totalis
- Alopecia universalis

Symptom:

This condition causes one or more circular patches where hair falls out. These patches can grow quickly. The skin in these patches looks normal and smooth. There may also be some white or broken hairs within these patches. Itching or burning may be

felt in the affected areas. The hair usually grows back, but this can take several months or even years. In some people, the hair never grows back.

Causes:

Alopecia areata is a common, non-contagious autoimmune disease characterized by patchy hair loss. In this condition, the immune system mistakenly targets the body's own healthy structures-specifically the hair follicles- as if they were foreign invaders. This autoimmune attack disrupts normal hair growth, leading to hair shafts breaking and falling out, primarily on the scalp. Your immune system attacks your hair follicles because it mistakenly identifies them as foreign invaders, such as bacteria, viruses, parasites, or fungi, which typically cause infection and disease. When this happens, your hair begins to fall out, often in clumps the size and shape of a quarter. The extent of hair loss varies. In some cases, it occurs in only a few spots. In other cases, the hair loss can be more severe, including complete hair loss.

Case History :

A 7-year-old male patient presented to the Outpatient Department (OPD) of Babu G. Ram Homoeopathic Clinic, Jaipur, Rajasthan, on May 15, 2024. The patient sought consultation for a primary complaint of patchy, typically round hair loss on the

scalp, which had been gradually progressing for several months and was associated with intermittent itching.

ADVISED FOR INVESTIGATION:

- CBC
- ESR
- CRP/LFT
- RFT/ELECTROLYTE
- TSH/T3/T4
- ANA
- VIT-D

Figure 1. Successful Homeopathic Treatment Outcomes for Alopecia Areata in a Paediatric Patient.

This composite image illustrates the progression of hair regrowth following homeopathic intervention.

Image: 1, 2, 3, 7: Show the initial presentation of the patient's scalp prior to the commencement of treatment, highlighting the extent of patchy hair loss.

Image: 4, 5, 6, 8, 9: Illustrate the condition of the scalp after treatment, demonstrating successful and significant hair regrowth across different views.

Analysis and evaluations

- Mental Generals
- Consolation aggravation
- Wants to be alone to cry
- Irritable

Physical Generals

Thirst: Thirsty

Thermal Reaction: Hot

Stool: Dry, Hard, Stitching pain after stool sometimes

Desire: Salty foods, table salt; ++

Modalities: <noise, consolation; >open air

Sweat: Offensive

Appetite: Hungry

Figure 2: Repertorial charts

Repertorisation						
Symptoms: 5 Remedies: 89 Applied Filter						
Remedy Name	Nat-m	Sil	Ign	Kali-c	Nit-ac	Sep
Totality / Symptom Covered	14 / 5	9 / 4	9 / 3	7 / 4	7 / 3	7 / 3
[Kent] [Stomach]Desires:Salt things: (30)	3				2	
[Kent] [Mind]Consolation :Agg: (23)	3	3	3	1	1	3
[Kent] [Rectum]Pain: Burning: Stool: After a hard: (23)	2	3		1		
[Kent] [Mind]Conversation agg (see talking): (35)	3	2	3	1		1
[Boenning] [Sweat]Aggravation:Eating:While:	3	1	3	4	4	3

Repertorial analysis & remedy selection

Post-repertorization evaluation indicated that *Natrum muriaticum* covered the maximum characteristic symptoms (Totality of Symptoms) of the case.

Follow up

The patient was initially prescribed *Natrum muriaticum* 30CH (thrice daily) for four days, followed by *Sac lac* (thrice daily) and diet management for 15 days. This treatment sequence was then repeated: *Natrum muriaticum* 30CH (thrice daily) for four days, followed by *Sac lac* (thrice daily) and diet management for 15 days. After two months, the patient received a single dose of *Natrum muriaticum* 200CH, followed by *Sac lac* (thrice daily) for 15 days. The follow-up regimen concluded after one month with *Sac lac* (thrice daily) administered for 15 days.

Discussion

This case report describes the successful homeopathic treatment of a seven-year-old child suffering from Alopecia. This case highlights the efficacy and safety of homeopathy as a therapeutic option for Alopecia, contrasting with conventional allopathic treatments which often merely control symptoms and carry associated side effects.

The regular intake of homeopathic medicine not only resulted in significant hair regrowth but also elicited positive changes in the child's confidence and overall mental state. Importantly, no adverse events were encountered throughout the treatment period.

Natrum muriaticum was identified as the most indicated

homeopathic remedy for this particular case. This selection was based on the comprehensive totality of the patient's symptoms, establishing a clear remedy picture as determined after consulting the Materia Medica.

Conclusion

The rapid and distinct symptomatic improvement observed following the initiation of homeopathic treatment highlights its profound therapeutic potential. This clinical outcome successfully demonstrates that when homeopathic principles are correctly utilized, even complex diseases can be effectively managed by selecting the appropriate individualized remedy based on the totality of symptoms.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

1. my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/12423-alopecia-areata
2. www.aad.org/public/diseases/hair-loss/types/alopecia
3. Repertory of Homoeopathic Materia-Medica, Dr. J.T Kent
4. Allen HC, Allen's Keynote
5. William. Boericke's pocket manual of Materia medica & Repertory